

Photovoltaics' marketability in private households in Bacoor City: A marketing strategy

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Abstract

The study investigated the marketability of photovoltaics in private households in Bacoor City, Cavite. The sample size (n) of 384 respondents was computed using the Solvin's formula in random sampling to give every respondent the chance to participate in the study. A reliability testing was done with 0.80 correlation results. Respondents voluntarily participated in the online survey form which contained questions regarding the respondent's demographic profile and statement questionnaire in a five-point Likert scale that determined the perception of the respondents of the use of photovoltaics in their private households in terms of: Usefulness, 4.42 average weighted mean; Savings of electricity expenses, 4.46 average weighted mean; Environmental support, 4.46 average weighted mean; and Knowledge about the technology, 4.53 average weighted mean. A simple marketing strategy was generated from the data gathered to help increase the marketability of photovoltaics.

Keywords: Photovoltaics; on-grid photovoltaics; marketing Ps; marketability; renewable energy.

To cite this article:

Alhambra, E. M., & Parceró, R. I. (2022). Photovoltaics' marketability in private households in Bacoor City: A marketing strategy. *The Executives*, 3, 1-11.

Introduction

We have hurt the planet in many ways for us to live comfortably and fine-tune it to our lifestyle. This is not only true in the Philippines but more so in the entire globe. While the population in the Philippines has rapidly grown since the second half of the last century and has continued to grow at an even faster pace during the last decade of this century, in line with the economic upturn, and the demand for electricity use in private residential homes increased accordingly. Moreover, since the beginning of 2020, the demand for electricity from private households has substantially increased and was particularly accentuated due to the spreading of the Covid-19 pandemic and the ensuing, quite restrictive quarantine measures put in place by the government. During the first months of the Quarantine with partial lockdowns, starting in March, many people were obliged to stay at home and, consequently, began losing their jobs. A report by the Philippine Statistics Authority (2020) regarding the employment situation in April 2020 showed an all-time high of the unemployment rate, namely reaching 17.6%, corresponding to nearly 6.4 million unemployed Filipinos compared to an unemployment rate of 5.1% or 2.3 million jobless people of the same month last year. Although, the unemployment rate was easing downwards to 10.0% or 4.6 million Filipinos unemployed in July 2020, it still has remained on a relatively high level compared with the same month the year before, namely at 5.4% corresponding to 2.5 million unemployed Filipinos.

This means that with the further spreading of the COVID-19 pandemic, more people than normally will be forced to stay at home, and it can be expected that short-term demand for electrical energy for private use will further increase. But also, over the medium- and long-term time horizon and, after the COVID-19 pandemic will have faded away, demand for electric energy in private households will continuously increase in future as the population will also continue to grow and, with an improvement of the living standard, more and more electricity consuming devices will come into use.

The 2019 Power Situation Report of the Department of Energy (2020) shows that the private residential sector represents the largest consumption share of total electricity sales (28.8%) followed by industrial (26.6%) and commercial at (24.0%). The DoE's recent Power Statistics released the electricity consumption across the archipelago grew by 6.3% in the previous year (2019) for about 106,041 gigawatt hours (GWh) from 99,765 GWh (2018) (Rudnick & Velasquez, 2019).

The COVID-19 pandemic has exposed the Philippine's weakness in the power market. The country relies mainly on imported fossil fuels which delivered due to fixed long-term contracts instead of a least cost system. This means, the country is tied up with price instability, inflexibility, and negative effects on the balance of trade. Due to such contracts, electricity prices are being changed depending on fossil fuel prices and are being passed down to consumers (Ahmed, 2020).

Ahmed (2018) explained the reliance on coal to generate power for electricity makes less and less sense due to the rapidly declining cost and technological advances in renewable energy. The Philippines' leading distributor utility (DU) is still using coal to generate power. An incident in 2016, where Panay Energy Development Corporation- a coal operator supplier of the utility company signed a deal to acquire coal-fire power at PHP 3.96/kWh. Due to the current situation and regulation in the Philippines, coal companies can change the actual cost. The coal company made their consumer pays 37% more at PHP 5.41/kWh. This expense will be passed through the DU's consumer – the public.

Solar energy makes more sense in the Philippines, and it provides an immediate solution to the country's energy problems. The potential power generating capacity for the northern part of the country is between 4.5-5 kWh per square meter per day, while the southern part of the country, where Bacoor City is located can produce an average of 5.0-5.5 kWh per square meter of solar power per day (Deutsche Gesellschaft für Internationale Zusammenarbeit et al., 2013).

Photovoltaic system are multiple solar panels combined with an inverter and other electrical hardware that uses energy from the Sun to generate electricity (Energy Education, n.d.). These systems can vary in size and can function off the grid. However, this study will focus only on the marketability of photovoltaic systems that are grid-tied. Grid tied PV systems are connected to the utility grid or the distribution utility (DU) as this is what is commonly being offered in the Philippines.

Photovoltaics are becoming popular and affordable each year. The solar grid system promises a lifespan of about 20-25 years or more and are being offered across the country. For this study, the researcher made an assumption of savings and computation below, since the Photovoltaic grid tied systems packages varies from different installation companies, different prices, and offers. The researcher used the PV grid tied packages available near the area of Bacoor City. The researcher consulted an engineer to determine what is the size of the photovoltaic technology needed for a private household in the city. Based from the results of the survey questionnaire from 384 respondents, it was found out that the average usage is around 314 kWh monthly usage. As suggested recommendation by Engineer Allan A. Roberto, a 3kWp grid tied system is needed for such a household with the calculation below:

$$\begin{aligned} 314 \text{ kWh}/30 \text{ days} &= 10.46 \text{ kWh per day usage} \\ 10.46 \text{ kWh}/4 \text{ hours (calculated average sunpeak)} \times 0.9 \text{ (inverter efficiency)} \\ &= 2.9 \text{ kWp or } 3\text{kWp grid tied system} \end{aligned}$$

As mentioned earlier, there are many different options for the photovoltaic system depending on a household's budget, whether it will be Chinese, Japanese, German, or Norway technology it comes in different price ranges and efficiency. The current price range around Bacoor City for a 3kwp grid tied system ranges from PhP 160,000 to 230,000. In Bacoor City, a few solar panel installation businesses are existing in the installation of photovoltaics. Assuming that a resident of Bacoor City has a 314-kWh monthly electricity usage acquires a 3kWp grid tied package with a contract price of PhP 160,000 that promises 20 years' warranty on solar panels.

Example computation / scenario:

314kWh x ₱8.5920 per kWh (May 2021 Meralco price) = estimated PhP 2,697.88 monthly bill (Rey, 2021)

Person A: No Grid tied system

Payment to Meralco PhP 32,374.56 annually, estimated payment for 20 years = PhP 647,000 (only estimation, no inflation rate calculation)

Person B: 3kWp grid tied system purchased cash basis (no loan)

Savings: PhP 32,374.56 annually, Return on Investment 4.94 years.

Savings after ROI for the next 15 years = PhP 485,618 (estimation only)

Person C: 3kWp grid tied system purchased through government loan/bank loan with 6.5 percent interest per annum

PhP 160,000 loan contract + PhP 52,000 interest rate (5 years) = total contract price PhP 212,000

ROI: 5 years, estimated savings of 485, 618 PHP for 15 years.

The Future is Solar Energy

Solar energy will be the future of energy sources especially for private households as solar panels are more portable and accessible than other renewable energy (RE) like hydropower, wind power, biomass or geothermal energy. According to Domingo (2018) the Philippines ranked number one among developing countries in Asia in terms of the use of photovoltaic systems for electricity generation and is fifth place worldwide. Within the last decades, solar panels became available for commercial use and has become affordable. The forecast made by the Department of Energy of the Philippines (DOE) stated that in 2020, solar panels prices will drop by fifty-five percent.

Statement of the Problem

The dependency of the country on long term contracts of imported fossil fuels made by utility companies is resulting in price instability for the consumers. Due to the increasing population in the Philippines and energy demands in the future, consumers will look for alternative ways to get sources of energy for electricity. A power forecast made by the Department of Energy expects to reach 30,189 megawatts (MW) or nearly 70% more than the current capacity in the country being supplied by existing power plants in year 2030 (Pangalangan, 2016).

The study is designed to investigate the marketability of photovoltaics in Bacoor City, Cavite as basis for developing the marketing strategy. It has sought to answer the following:

1. What is the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1 age;

- 1.2 gender;
 - 1.3 occupation;
 - 1.4 civil status;
 - 1.5 gross household income; and
 - 1.6 ownership of the house (rent or homeowner)?
2. What are the perceptions of the respondents in the use of photovoltaics in their private households in terms of:
 - 2.1 Usefulness;
 - 2.2 savings to electricity expenses;
 - 2.3 environmental support; and
 - 2.4 knowledge about the PV technology?
 3. What marketing strategy can be developed to increase PV marketability?

Hypothesis

1. There is no significant difference between usefulness and savings to electricity expenses.
2. There is no significant difference between environmental support/or contribution and knowledge about photovoltaics.
3. There is no significant difference between savings to electricity expenses and knowledge about photovoltaics.

Scope and Limitation of the Study

This study started last September 2020 to May 2021 and the residents of Bacoor City has been chosen as the respondents of this research. Individuals residing outside Bacoor City are excluded in the study to delimit the scope. This study has not covered broader topics related to marketability for other renewable energy (RE). Solar power is the main topic explored and discussed relative to the marketability of photovoltaics in the area of Bacoor City. Each respondent of the study was provided the questionnaires to answer. The main source in data gathering and in identifying the marketability of photovoltaics in the Bacoor City is the research-made questionnaire.

Methodology

Research Design

The researcher formulated a set of survey questionnaire form for the respondents. The researcher used the descriptive method in a qualitative analysis to investigate the marketability of photovoltaics and solar power for residential use in Bacoor City, Cavite, Philippines.

Sample

The study requires diverse individuals coming from different areas of Bacoor City. Random sampling and volunteer individuals from different age groups, different gender, status, and income bracket to insure the strength of the study. Using Slovin's formula and an estimated population of Bacoor City of 686,398 with a 95 percent confidence level and 5 percent margin of error, the computed value is $N =$ three hundred eighty-four (384).

Sampling Procedures

The researcher secured an approval from SDCA Research Ethics Committee (REC) to ensure that ethical protocols are followed. The survey questionnaire before being finalized and distributed to the respondents was checked by the Research and Development Office of St. Dominic College of Asia. Each respondent answered the online questionnaire within five minutes and each individual was aware that the data being collected were for the use of this study. The researcher made sure that the data were treated with utmost confidentiality and only the researcher has access to the file containing all the data and no respondents were named together with the data presented in the study. Since March 2020 we have been in a general community quarantine (lockdown) due to the coronavirus pandemic, the researcher has to work from home. The questionnaire was distributed using a Google survey form and distributed through emails, and online social media groups to the respondents of the different Barangays of Bacoor City.

Instruments

The researcher has prepared an online questionnaire through the use of google forms as an instrument in the gathering and collection of data from the respondents. The questionnaire was evaluated by the adviser of the researcher and by a member of the Research and Development Office of St. Dominic College of Asia before being distributed to the respondents. The questionnaire used a five-point Likert scale: Strongly Agree, Agree, Moderately Agree, Disagree, and Strongly Disagree to measure the respondent's attitude with a particular question or statement. The first part of the survey form was the respondent's demographic profile. Second, the respondents were asked in to determine the marketability of photovoltaics and the respondent's perceptions of the use of the photovoltaics system in terms of usefulness, savings to electricity expenses, knowledge about PV systems, and environmental support. The research questionnaire was validated using the Cronbach's alpha reliability test with fifteen (15) pilot testers. The reliability score was at of 0.80.

Data Collection

The researcher used an online survey form to collect the respondent's data. Following the Data Privacy Act of 2012 of the Philippines and with the respondent's consent, each respondent has to sign their name in the online form and confirm to participate to the study before they can actually proceed to the online survey questionnaire. The researcher has treated the data with utmost confidentiality and no names or location, and any other sensitive information has been revealed. The data collected is only used for the purpose of completing this study. The study sought to find the marketability of photovoltaics (PV) for residential use. The researcher presented tables with frequency, percentage and a descriptive analysis to express the results.

Ethical Considerations

The researcher secured a consent and assent form from the Research Ethics Committee of SDCA. All respondents of the study voluntarily participated, and the researcher secured an online form permission to collect the data from all the respondents and the researcher explained to the respondents how their data will be treated in the study. All respondents were literate. They can read, write, and understand both the English and Filipino languages.

Results and Discussion

Demographic Profile

Table 1 presents the frequency and percentage distribution of the respondents' demographic profile. In terms of gender, it shows that 271 or 70.57 percent of the respondents are females and 113 or 29.42 percent respondents are males. In terms of age, it shows that 179 or 46.61 percent of the respondents belong to age range of 20 - 29 years of age; 187 or 48.69 percent are within the 30-49 age range; 18 or 4.68 percent belong to age above 50 years of age range. This reveals that majority of the respondents belong to the more productive and has the capacity to avail the photovoltaic system.

In terms of occupation, it shows that 58 or 15.10 percent are homemakers; 206 or 53.64 percent are employed; 116 or 30.20 percent are self-employed; and only 4 or 1.04% are retired or pensioners. This underscores the reality that a better overview on who belong to the productive group and who could avail of the photovoltaics even on installment basis. In terms of civil status, two-hundred ten (210) or 54.68 percent are single; 160 or 41.66 percent of the respondents are married; 10 or 2.60 percent are separated; and 4 or 1.04 percent are widowed.

In terms of gross family income, thirty (30) or 7.81 percent of respondents belong to the gross family income group of PhP 0-5,000; 43 or 11.19 percent are from PhP 5,001-10,000; 27 or 7.03 percent are from PhP 10,001-15,001 percent; 30 or 7.81 percent are from PhP 15,001-20,000; 37 or 9.63 percent are from PhP 20,001-25,000; 18 or 4.68 percent are from PhP 25,001-30,000 income group; 32 or 8.33 percent are from PhP 30,001-35,000 income group; 33 or 8.59 percent are from PhP 35,001-40,000 income group and lastly, 134 or 34.89 percent of the respondents are from the PhP 40,001 and above income group. This data could be deduced that majority of the residents of Bacoor City belong to the lower middle income and middle to middle class and up, based on the income groups in 2018 (Albert et al., 2020). In terms of their current housing ownership, majority of the respondents or 264 or 68.75 percent answered that they own the house that they are currently living in. While 120 or 31.25 percent respondents said that they are renting. More than half of the respondents residing in Bacoor own a house that can apply for photovoltaics for their housing.

Table 1. Demographic profile of the respondents (N=384)

Profile	Variables	Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Female	271	70.57%
	Male	113	29.42%
Age Range	20-29	179	46.61%
	30-49	187	48.69%
	Above 50	18	4.68%
Occupation	Homemaker	58	15.10%
	Employed	206	53.64%
	Self-employed	116	30.20%
	Retired / pensioners	4	1.04%
Civil Status	Single	210	54.68%
	Married	160	41.66%
	Separated	10	2.60%
	Widowed	4	1.04%
Gross Family Income (PhP)	0 - 5,000	30	7.81%
	5,001 - 10,000	43	11.19%
	10,001 - 15,000	27	7.03%
	15,001 – 20,000	30	7.81%
	20,001 – 25,000	37	9.63%
	25,001 – 30,000	18	4.68%
	30,001 – 35,000	32	8.33%
	35,001 – 40,000	33	8.59%
40,001 and above	134	34.89%	
Housing Ownership	Owner	264	68.75%
	Renter	120	31.25%

Perceptions of the Respondents to the Use of Photovoltaics in their Private Households

Table 2. Weighted mean distribution regarding the usefulness of photovoltaics

Usefulness	Weighted Mean	Standard Deviation	Results
I like that I can sell my excess electricity in a month to any electric company.	4.04	0.8659	4.42 (Agree)
I believe that the solar panels are an alternative source of electricity for my household.	4.63	0.6121	
I find the solar panels useful because I can generate my own electricity at home.	4.58	0.5984	

Legend: 1.00-1.49 – Strongly Disagree; 1.50-2.49 – Disagree; 2.50-3.49 – Moderately Agree; 3.50-4.49 – Agree; 4.50-5.00 – Strongly Agree

Table 2 indicates that the residents of Bacoor city, Cavite agree with the usefulness of Photovoltaics. As they expressed that: I believe that the solar panels are alternative source of electricity for my household (4.63, strongly agree); I find the solar panels useful because I can generate my own electricity at home (4.58, strongly agree); and they agree on liking the ability to sell excess electricity in a month to an electricity company (4.04).

Table 3. Weighted mean distribution regarding the savings to electricity expenses of photovoltaics

Savings to Electricity Expenses	Weighted Mean	Standard Deviation	Results
I believe that solar panels are a good investment.	4.51	0.6966	4.46 (Agree)
I believe that the money I earned by selling excess electricity will help me save money.	4.33	0.7544	
I know that the use of solar panels can save me money in the future.	4.56	0.6670	

Legend: 1.00-1.49 – Strongly Disagree; 1.50-2.49 – Disagree; 2.50-3.49 – Moderately Agree; 3.50-4.49 – Agree; 4.50-5.00 – Strongly Agree

Table 3 shows that residents of Bacoor City agree on the statements about photovoltaics when it comes to savings to electricity expenses. As they said that: I know that the use of photovoltaics can save me money in the future (4.56, strongly agree); I believe that photovoltaics are good investments when it comes to savings from electricity expenses (4.51, strongly agree); and I believe that money could be earned by selling excess electricity will help me save money (4.33, agree).

Table 4. Weighted mean distribution regarding the environmental support

Environmental Support	Weighted Mean	Standard Deviation	Results
I believe that solar panels are environmental-friendly.	4.59	0.6309	4.54 (Strongly Agree)
I believe that the energy that we use for electricity could not harm the earth.	4.54	0.6989	
I believe that harnessing the energy from the sun is better than the others.	4.44	0.7171	
I believe that using solar power energy as electricity reduces pollution.	4.57	0.6703	

Legend: 1.00-1.49 – Strongly Disagree; 1.50-2.49 – Disagree; 2.50-3.49 – Moderately Agree; 3.50-4.49 – Agree; 4.50-5.00 – Strongly Agree

Table 4 presents that the majority of residents in Bacoor City strongly agree that solar panels are environmental-friendly (4.59), and they agree that harnessing the energy from the sun is better than the others (4.44). Other statements are the following: I believe that using solar energy as electricity reduces pollution (4.57, strongly agree); and I believe that the energy we use for electricity could not harm the earth, (4.54, strongly agree).

Table 5. Weighted mean distribution regarding their knowledge about photovoltaics in general

Environmental Support	Weighted Mean	Standard Deviation	Results
I have heard or know about solar panels.	4.55	0.6234	4.64
I know that the sun’s energy can be converted into electricity for our homes.	4.77	0.4379	(Strongly Agree)
I know that solar panels can be installed in houses to help of reducing the monthly electricity bills.	4.72	0.5241	
I know that solar panels can be installed in houses to help eliminate electricity expenses.	4.63	0.6132	
I believe that the Philippines has a lot of potential when it comes to solar energy.	4.55	0.7135	

Legend: 1.00-1.49 – Strongly Disagree; 1.50-2.49 – Disagree; 2.50-3.49 – Moderately Agree; 3.50-4.49 – Agree; 4.50-5.00 – Strongly Agree

Table 5 illustrates that majority of the residents agree about solar panel. As they argued that: I believe that the Philippines has a lot of potential when it comes to solar energy (4.55, strongly agree); I know that the sun’s energy can be converted into electricity for our homes (4.77, strongly agree); solar panels can be installed in houses to help of reducing the monthly electricity bills (4.75, strongly agree) and to help eliminate electricity expenses (4.63, strongly agree); have heard about the information on solar panels (4.55, strongly agree).

Marketing Strategy to Increase PV Marketability

The gathered results illustrate that the perception of respondents in the use of photovoltaics in terms of: a.) Usefulness; b.) Savings to electricity expenses; c.) Environmental support; and d.) Knowledge about the PV technology. All four variables show the results in agreement, and this will be used to come up with a simple marketing plan with the use of the marketing Ps as a marketing strategy to drive marketability of the photovoltaics.

Hypothesis

For this study, a t-test was conducted to test the significant difference within the groups to make a decision to accept or reject the hypothesis.

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference between usefulness and savings to electricity expenses.

Table 6. t-Test: Two-Sample Assuming Equal Variances (Usefulness of photovoltaic system vs Savings to electricity expenses)

	Variable 1	Variable 2
Mean	4.416666667	4.466667
Variance	0.107033333	0.014633
Observations	3	3
Pooled Variance	0.060833333	
Hypothesized Mean Difference	0	
df	4	
t Stat	-0.248281767	
P(T<=t) one-tail	0.40807101	
t Critical one-tail	2.131846786	
P(T<=t) two-tail	0.81614202	
t Critical two-tail	2.776445105	

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant difference between environmental support/or contribution and knowledge about photovoltaics.

Table 7. t-Test: Two-Sample Assuming Unequal Variances (Environmental support vs knowledge about photovoltaics)

	Variable 1	Variable 2
Mean	4.535	4.7646
Variance	0.004433333	0.020571
Observations	4	5
Hypothesized Mean Difference	0	
df	6	
t Stat	-3.177115012	
P(T<=t) one-tail	0.009572802	
t Critical one-tail	1.943180281	
P(T<=t) two-tail	0.019145605	
t Critical two-tail	2.446911851	

Hypothesis 3: There is no significant difference between savings and knowledge about PV.

Table 8. t-Test: Two-Sample assuming Unequal Variances (Savings to electricity expenses vs knowledge about photovoltaics)

	Variable 1	Variable 2
Mean	4.466666667	4.535
Variance	0.014633333	0.004433333
Observations	3	4
Hypothesized Mean Difference	0	
df	3	
t Stat	-0.883202357	
P(T<=t) one-tail	0.221083843	
t Critical one-tail	2.353363435	
P(T<=t) two-tail	0.442167686	
t Critical two-tail	3.182446305	

Table 9. Summary of test results of difference between variables

Variable	Statistics	Degree of freedom	Computed value	Critical value
Usefulness vs Savings	t	4	-0.2483	2.7764
Environmental vs knowledge	t	6	-3.1771	2.4469
Savings vs knowledge	t	3	-0.8832	3.1824

The difference between the variables under study were determined using t-test. From the table, the observed t-value (-0.2483) for the opinions or perceptions of respondents on usefulness and savings is less than the critical value (2.7764), hence, not enough evidence to show that difference exist. In like manner, the perceptions of respondents between environmental support and knowledge about solar panels has no difference since the computed t-value (-3.1771) is less than the tabular value (2.4469). Moreover, on the difference between savings to electricity expenses and knowledge about solar panels, there is no difference on the respondents' opinions or perceptions. This implies that there is no difference exists on the perceptions of respondents towards knowledge, usefulness of solar panels, savings to electricity expenses, and environmental support. As based from the computations above, the decision is to fail to reject the null hypothesis.

Marketing P mix based on results

1. **Product:** Grid tied photovoltaic system for residential house at least 3kwp. Based on the average energy consumption of Bacoor City residents.
2. **Price:** Based from the gathered data, 97% will avail PV systems for their households as long as a low interest contract will be offered. The respondents of Bacoor City are also willing to buy when PV systems are affordable compared to other systems in the market.
3. **People:** Mostly female, some are males. Ages 30-39 years old who were employed, self-employed or has a small business.
4. **Promotion:** The respondents of Bacoor City are also willing to buy when PV systems are affordable compared to other systems in the market, limited time offers or discounts and when installment programs are presented to the consumers.
5. **Place:** From the collected data, the residents of Bacoor City prefers the advertisement to be done online or digital marketing through Google searches, websites, and social media marketing.
6. **Process:** Uncomplicated process and provided assistance on how to apply for the net metering with Meralco will most likely lead to more residents availing photovoltaics from the residents of Bacoor.
7. **Physical Evidence:** Based on collected data, the residents of Bacoor will be more interested if the photovoltaics are marketed using the results above or using usefulness, savings to electricity expenses, environmental support and the respondent's knowledge about PV technology.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The majority of the respondents agreed that photovoltaics were useful, which increased their savings as to electricity consumption, and protected the environment. In like manner, majority of the respondents were knowledgeable about photovoltaics. The findings reached in this study may lend thoughts to the reduction of the use of fuel or coal in the production of electricity, instead rely upon the natural process of producing electricity which is environment-friendly that would support global intention as contained in the Paris Agreement of 2015.

Solar panels are useful because it could generate electricity at home at a lower expense and create a feeling of financial independence from electricity companies. Moreover, the solar panel could raise the momentum of enthusiasm and motivation to save money which has usually been a big chunk on the family income in payment of electricity bill. Further, the use of it is environment-friendly, hence; the use of PV marketability is encouraged. Finally, it is suggested that business owners should focus on how does the technology work from the conversion of solar energy to the photovoltaics to household use and more importantly how does it go to the power grid of the electricity company and convert it to more savings. Further research may be conducted to validate the findings of the present study and may involve other variables not covered.

Acknowledgments

An expression of thanks to our professor in thesis writing, Dr. Nilda W. Balsicas, who has been patient with all of us; who have guided us with passion by giving us the advices to improve my paper, and for believing in me and the rest. To my adviser, Dr. Romeo Parcero for the encouragement, guidance, patience and all the lessons I have learned while writing this paper. To the panel members, for all the constructive remarks on my paper. It was the best experience of my life and thank you for all of your suggestions in the making of a better MBA paper. To the engineers and business owners, for their valuable suggestions which led to a better understanding on the technical side of the study. To the three hundred

eighty-four (384) residents across the 73 barangays of Bacoor City for their involvement as respondents of the study and the valuable information they have provided to complete the data gathering. To Dr. Gerald Ocan, Dean of School of Business and Computer Studies for his insightful thoughts, time with the researcher, and intellectual inputs for all the students despite limited resources – human and non-human.

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